

How Predictable are the Academy Awards?

Working Paper

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Summary

By conducting an explorative study it is tried to determine whether a sample of film enthusiasts can produce a similar result in judging for the 87th Academy Awards for movies in 2014 like the actual Academy members or not. An online survey has been created and the votes cast by the participants have been tabulated. It can be shown that the results of the simulated awards voting in the survey are quite similar to the actual Academy decision. However, additional adjustments and further studies are recommended to ensure the results.

Key Words Academy Awards; instant runoff voting; ballot; relative majority; predictability; film; motion pictures; United States of America; study; survey

Introduction

Year after year, the motion picture awards season in the United States of America closes with the Academy Awards ceremony. The Oscars, as the awards are colloquially known, are supposed to be the world's most important motion picture awards. All active members of the so-called Academy of Motion Pictures Arts and Science (AMPAS) are eligible to vote for the Oscars. But is there a certain chance to predict the winners by using a sample of film lovers and awards aficionados who vote on an online survey? And how close may these people get to the actual results?

The Academy Awards

The Academy does make some secrecy about the exact number and composition of the Academy members. A *Los Angeles Times* study from 2012 concluded that there are 5765 voting members who "are nearly 94% Caucasian and 77% male [...]. Blacks are about 2% of the academy, and Latinos are less than 2%. Oscar voters have a median age of 62 [...]. People younger than 50 constitute just 14% of the membership" (LA Times 2012).

Voting on the Oscars is a complicated process with multiple stages. First of all, the Academy sets up rules regarding the eligibility and voting procedures in every year. Generally, all feature films that have been exhibited in a theatre in the Los Angeles County for at least seven days throughout a year will qualify for the Academy Awards (AMPAS 2014, 2-3). This rule applies for films from all countries given that they are in the English language or English subtitles are provided (AMPAS 2014, 4). However,

there are special eligibility rules for short films, foreign language films and documentaries.

Each year the Academy produces a list of eligible films from which the Academy members select up to five nominees per category (except for Makeup, which calls for three nominations, and Best Picture in which up to ten nominees may be chosen).

As for the 87th Academy Awards which honors films of 2014, the following 24 categories were in use:

1. Actor in a Leading Role
2. Actor in a Supporting Role
3. Actress in a Leading Role
4. Actress in a Supporting Role
5. Animated Feature Film
6. Cinematography
7. Costume Design
8. Directing
9. Documentary (Feature)
10. Documentary (Short Subject)
11. Film Editing
12. Foreign Language Film
13. Makeup and Hairstyling
14. Music (Original Score)
15. Music (Original Song)
16. Best Picture
17. Production Design
18. Short Film (Animated)
19. Short Film (Live Action)
20. Sound Editing
21. Sound Mixing
22. Visual Effects
23. Writing (Adapted Screenplay)
24. Writing (Original Screenplay)

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The Academy consists of different branches in which certain professions are organized, e. g. directors, writers, cinematographers etc. As a general rule, only members of a branch may choose the nominees in the respective category. Members of the director's branch vote for directors, members of the actor's branch for all acting categories and so on. For Best Picture, all members are entitled to choose the nominees. "There is no guarantee, however, that this august group of voters will actually have *seen* the films they tick on the list of eligible candidates sent out to them each January. Busy moguls have been known to let their secretaries or mistresses mark their cards for them" (Holden 1993, 36). The exact voting procedures for the nominations may differ throughout the categories (AMPAS 2014, 5-6). For most categories, members vote in order of their preference for five nominees. Some nominee lists are made up by special committees (e.g. for Animated Feature) For the Documentary awards, a shortlist is created from which the final nominees are selected.

After tabulating the results and revealing the nominations to the public, final voting begins. At this stage, all active Academy members are eligible to vote in each category. In 23 of 24 categories, the nominee which receives the most votes is awarded with the Academy Award (relative majority). Voting figures are never revealed by the Academy, "so no one [...] knows what percentage of the electorate actually return their ballots—rumored to be less than half—or who beat whom by what margin" (Holden 1993, 37).

However, for Best Picture the voting members have to rank all nominees. Here, an instant runoff voting system applies. Ballots are initially tabulated based on each voter's first preference. If a nominee secures more than half of votes cast, that nominee wins instantly. Otherwise, the nominee with the fewest votes is eliminated. Ballots assigned to the eliminated nominee are recounted and assigned to those of the remaining nominees who rank next in order of preference on each ballot. This process continues until one nominee wins by obtaining more than half the votes.

A voting member does not need to fill out every category. If he or she does not feel qualified enough to judge the Academy encourages to leave categories unmarked (Variety 2015).

Setting up the survey

This study is of an explorative nature, inspired by a remark by Anthony Holden: "Do set designers know much about music? Or sound men about editing? Or actors about cinematography? Not much more than

the average moviegoer, but that's the way the system works" (Holden 1993, 37).

Therefore, we have set up a questionnaire that essentially reflects the official Oscar voting ballot and asked people from certain online communities to vote on their favorite nominees. It has been pointed out that all participants shall indeed vote for their favorites and specifically not to try to make a prediction about what the Academy members will decide. To achieve this, the nominees from all the categories were presented to the participants in alphabetical order. Every participant was able to cast one vote per category (or make no choice) and was asked to rank the nominees for Best Picture. At the end of the survey, every participant was asked to complete a short social-demographic query on age, sex, country of origin, and education.

Participants were recruited by placing calls on several Facebook groups and dedicated award discussion forums. Overall, these groups and forums have been used:

- Facebook groups
 - Classic Film Lovers' Haven
 - Doktoranden Kommunikations- und Medienwissenschaften
 - Film Lover
 - Filmwissenschaft/Film Studies
 - HFF München Schwarzes Brett
 - Junge Filmemacher
 - KMWler Uni Leipzig
 - NECS European Network for Cinema and Media Studies
 - Noir Film Lovers
 - Orchestration Online
- Forums
 - Awardswatch.com
 - Goldderby.com
 - IMDb
 - Rottentomatoes.com
 - Uaadb.cinemasight.com

The survey was done by using the online survey portal *SoSciSurvey.de*. As this study was meant to be only a first tryout in predicting the Oscars, it was determined that the survey was open to everyone and not restricted to a certain panel. Alas, it may have been possible to vote more than once. For future studies, creating a distinct panel of voters who are to be personally invited to vote may be an option.

The survey was open to the public from February 10, 2015 to February 21, 2015.

General results

In total, 385 ballots have been cast in the survey. 325 ballots have been filled out completely. How-

ever, it was decided that every ballot was considered eligible for counting even if only a few categories have been filled out. This was done because an Academy member would have the opportunity to do the same thing in reality. In the online survey, it was impossible to make a ballot invalid, for example by adding a “write-in” candidate.

According to the Academy rules, the votes for each category were tabulated and the nominees which received most of the votes won. For Best Picture, the votes were tabulated according to the instant runoff voting system. The online survey would only allow to assign one rank to one film. It was not possible to rank two films on one rank. However, the participants were able to rank only some nominees, or to begin with a lower rank than 1st or omitting a rank in the middle (e.g. ranking 1, 2, 3, omitting 4, and proceeding with 5). In these cases, these omissions were not counted and a ballot in which only a part of the nominees were ranked 5th to 8th place, for example, was handled as being ranked 1st to 4th. However, if all ranks were eliminated during tabulating that ballot was deleted from the final round of tabulating.

In the survey, some socio-demographic data was also asked to provide the ability to correlate certain data to sex, age, or country of origin.

Nearly two-thirds of the participants are male, only a fifth of them is female (chart 1). In this aspect, the sample shows certain similarities to the Academy membership roster which is also dominated by men.

Chart 1: Socio-demographics (sex)

Vice-versa, the voters in this survey proved to be very young in comparison to the Academy. 73 percent of the voters are below the age of 40 (chart 2). The majority of all participants do have at least a Bachelor degree (chart 3).

Regarding the country of origin, the survey is truly international. Although the majority of voters originate from the United States of America (a quarter in total), we have participants from another 47 countries from all over the world. There is a huge German bias that may be partly due to the fact that the study was conceived and based in Germany. Unfortunately, 27 percent of the participants chose not to reveal their country of origin (chart 4).

Chart 2: Socio-demographics (age)

Chart 3: Socio-demographics (education)

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Chart 4: Socio-demographics (country of origin)

The actual Academy Awards were conferred on February 22, 2015. The following chart lists all winners and the outcomes of this study.

Furthermore, in the following diagrams the tabulated votes in all categories are shown. For each category, the size of the statistical sample is given (n=).

Only if a category has been voted for, the vote is shown in these diagrams. Abstentions are not displayed but will be discussed in a separate chapter. Therefore, the number of “n” can be smaller than the actual size of total counted ballots (385).

	Winner at the Academy Awards	Winner of the survey	Runner-up of the survey
Actor in a Leading Role	Eddie Redmayne	Michael Keaton	Eddie Redmayne
Actor in a Supporting Role	J.K. Simmons	J.K. Simmons	
Actress in a Leading Role	Julianne Moore	Julianne Moore	
Actress in a Supporting Role	Patricia Arquette	Patricia Arquette	
Animated Feature Film	Big Hero 6	The Tale of the Princess Kaguya	How to Train Your Dragon 2
Cinematography	Birdman (or The Unexpected Virtue of Ignorance)	Birdman (or The Unexpected Virtue of Ignorance)	
Costume Design	The Grand Budapest Hotel	The Grand Budapest Hotel	
Directing	Birdman (or The Unexpected Virtue of Ignorance)	Boyhood	Birdman (or The Unexpected Virtue of Ignorance)
Documentary (Feature)	Citizenfour	Citizenfour	
Documentary (Short Subject)	Crisis Hotline: Veterans Press 1	White Earth	Crisis Hotline: Veterans Press 1
Film Editing	Whiplash	Whiplash	
Foreign Language Film	Ida	Ida	
Makeup and Hairstyling	The Grand Budapest Hotel	The Grand Budapest Hotel	

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Music (Original Score)	The Grand Budapest Hotel	The Grand Budapest Hotel	
Music (Original Song)	Selma	The Lego Movie	Selma
Best Picture	Birdman (or The Unexpected Virtue of Ignorance)	Boyhood	The Grand Budapest Hotel
Production Design	The Grand Budapest Hotel	The Grand Budapest Hotel	
Short Film (Animated)	Feast	Feast	
Short Film (Live Action)	The Phone Call	The Phone Call	
Sound Editing	American Sniper	Interstellar	Birdman (or The Unexpected Virtue of Ignorance)
Sound Mixing	Whiplash	Whiplash	
Visual Effects	Interstellar	Interstellar	
Writing (Adapted Screenplay)	The Imitation Game	Whiplash	Inherent Vice
Writing (Original Screenplay)	Birdman (or The Unexpected Virtue of Ignorance)	The Grand Budapest Hotel	Birdman or (The Unexpected Virtue of Ignorance)

Table 1: Summary of all winners of the 87th Academy Awards and of the survey. Bold typeface indicates matches.

In total, 15 out of 24 categories were predicted accurately. For another five categories, the actual winners were at least runners-up in the survey. This is a rate of 62.5 percent of correct predictions or, if you also count the runners-up, even a rate of 83.3 percent. For the remaining four categories including Best Picture, the actual winners matches the second

runner-up in the respective categories after all (table 1).

If we compare the Academy Awards winners to five randomly selected single ballots of the survey (which were filled out completely) we get the following results:

	Ballot #98	Ballot #307	Ballot #650	Ballot #692	Ballot #710
Actor in a Leading Role	Michael Keaton	Michael Keaton	Michael Keaton	Bradley Cooper	Michael Keaton
Actor in a Supporting Role	J.K. Simmons	J.K. Simmons	J.K. Simmons	Mark Ruffalo	Mark Ruffalo
Actress in a Leading Role	Julianne Moore	Julianne Moore	Reese Witherspoon	Marion Cotillard	Rosamund Pike
Actress in a Supporting Role	Emma Stone	Laura Dern	Keira Knightley	Patricia Arquette	Patricia Arquette
Animated Feature Film	How To Train Your Dragon 2	Big Hero 6	Big Hero 6	The Tale of the Princess Kaguya	The Tale of the Princess Kaguya
Cinematography	Birdman (or The Unexpected Virtue of Ignorance)	Unbroken	Birdman (or The Unexpected Virtue of Ignorance)	Ida	Birdman (or The Unexpected Virtue of Ignorance)
Costume Design	Inherent Vice	Maleficent	The Grand Budapest Hotel	Inherent Vice	The Grand Budapest Hotel
Directing	Birdman (or The Unexpected Virtue of Ignorance)	Birdman (or The Unexpected Virtue of Ignorance)	Birdman (or The Unexpected Virtue of Ignorance)	The Grand Budapest Hotel	Boyhood
Documentary (Feature)	Citizenfour	Last Days in Vietnam	The Salt of the Earth	Citizenfour	Citizenfour
Documentary (Short Subject)	Crisis Hotline: Veterans Press 1	Our Curse	Crisis Hotline: Veterans Press 1	Joanna	Crisis Hotline: Veterans Press 1
Film Editing	Whiplash	American Sniper	Whiplash	American Sniper	Boyhood
Foreign Language Film	Leviathan	Leviathan	Ida	Ida	Ida
Makeup and Hairstyling	The Grand Budapest Hotel	Foxcatcher	The Grand Budapest Hotel	Guardians of the Galaxy	Guardians of the Galaxy
Music (Original Score)	The Theory of Everything	Interstellar	The Grand Budapest Hotel	The Grand Budapest Hotel	The Theory of Everything
Music (Original Song)	The Lego Movie	The Lego Movie	Selma	The Lego Movie	The Lego Movie
Best Picture	Birdman (or The Unexpected Virtue of Ignorance)	American Sniper	Whiplash	American Sniper	Boyhood
Production Design	The Grand Budapest Hotel	The Grand Budapest Hotel	The Grand Budapest Hotel	The Grand Budapest Hotel	The Grand Budapest Hotel

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Short Film (Animated)	The Bigger Picture	The Dam Keeper	Feast	Feast	Feast
Short Film (Live Action)	Boogaloo and Graham	Butter Lamp	Butter Lamp	The Phone Call	The Phone Call
Sound Editing	Birdman (or The Unexpected Virtue of Ignorance)	Interstellar	Birdman (or The Unexpected Virtue of Ignorance)	American Sniper	American Sniper
Sound Mixing	Whiplash	American Sniper	Whiplash	American Sniper	Whiplash
Visual Effects	Guardians of the Galaxy	Dawn of the Planets of the Apes	Dawn of the Planets of the Apes	Guardians of the Galaxy	Interstellar
Writing (Adapted Screenplay)	Inherent Vice	American Sniper	Whiplash	Inherent Vice	Whiplash
Writing (Original Screenplay)	Birdman (or The Unexpected Virtue of Ignorance)	Nightcrawler	Birdman (or The Unexpected Virtue of Ignorance)	The Grand Budapest Hotel	Nightcrawler
Matches total	12	5	15	8	12

Table 2: Summary of results of five randomly selected ballots from the survey. Bold typeface indicates matches with the actual Academy Awards winners.

Ballot #650 draws equal to the overall result of 15 correct predictions but, however, the other ballots significantly perform less. Two things in this chart are of special interest. First, the award for Production Design was given unanimously to *The Grand Budapest Hotel*. Second, none of the ballots shown above chose *The Imitation Game* for Best Adapted Screenplay or Eddie Redmayne for Best Leading Actor.

We will now have a closer look on single categories in the survey to show which awards were in a neck-and-neck race.

Best Picture

The Best Picture category is exceptional in terms of tabulating the final votes. If the votes were tabulated as they are in the other categories, a relative majority of 10 percent plus one vote would be sufficient enough for a Best Picture win with ten nominees. Therefore, as mentioned above, the Academy employs an instant runoff voting to ensure that the final winner of the category has substantial support throughout the voters.

The tabulating in this survey was done in the same manner as the Academy's. Initially, the votes were tabulated for the first preference. The results of the first round of tabulating are shown in table 3.

American Sniper	16
Birdman or (The Unexpected Virtue of Ignorance)	69
Boyhood	97
The Grand Budapest Hotel	72
The Imitation Game	8
Selma	15
The Theory of Everything	8
Whiplash	41
n=	326
Droop quota	164

Table 3: Results of first ranks within the category Best Picture

We have a total sample of 326 votes which means that 164 votes are needed for a win in this round. This quota is called *Droop quota*. Note that from the beginning there is a triple-lead between *Birdman*, *Boyhood*, and *The Grand Budapest Hotel* from the beginning with the second and third ranked coming very close at only a three-vote difference. As there is no winner in the first round, the nominee with the fewest votes will be eliminated from now on. In this case, we have a tie at the end of the ranking with *The Imitation Game* and *The Theory of Everything* which means that the two films will be eliminated simultaneously. Votes on the ballots which ranked these two films first are now redistributed on the remaining ballots. This procedure will be repeated until one film has reached the quota.

I have arranged the whole process in table 4.

	1st round	2nd round	3rd round	4th round	5th round	6th round
<i>American Sniper</i>	16	18	<i>21</i>			
<i>Birdman or (The Unexpected Virtue of Ignorance)</i>	69	71	73	80	99	
Boyhood	97	100	105	109	123	169
<i>The Grand Budapest Hotel</i>	72	78	84	88	103	155
<i>The Imitation Game</i>	8					
<i>Selma</i>	15	<i>17</i>				
<i>The Theory of Everything</i>	8					
<i>Whiplash</i>	41	42	43	48		
n=	326	326	326	325	325	324
Droop quota	164	164	164	163	163	163

Table 4: Determining winner for Best Picture category. Bold typeface indicates 1st place. Italic typeface indicates nominees with the fewest votes per round.

It is noticeable that *Boyhood* is always in the lead, followed by *The Grand Budapest Hotel* in second and *Birdman* in third. Looking at the other nominations, only *Whiplash* was able to achieve a larger number of votes. Apparently, most voters yet preferred the three movies in the lead when ranking their preferences. This is most evident in *Whiplash*. After eliminating half of the nominees, *Whiplash* only got seven more votes while the first three achieved much higher growths. It is also remarkable how close the competition between *Birdman* and *The Grand Budapest Hotel* remains. After the 5th round, there is only a difference of four votes. So it is very likely that if *Birdman* had won the 5th round over *The Grand Budapest Hotel* it would have been a close heat between *Birdman* and *Boyhood*—thus reflecting the actual voting of the Academy members.

You may have noticed that the size of the sample decreases slightly as tabulating progresses. This occurs when someone did not rank all films. At some point, that ballot runs out of votes and is eliminated completely from the tabulation. As a side effect, the quota also decreases.

Details from other categories

Acting

There were hardly surprises in the acting categories. As expected, both awards for Supporting Actor/Actress went to the predicted forerunners. In the survey, both winners achieved 44 percent (J.K. Simmons for Supporting Actor) and 47 percent (Patricia Arquette for Supporting Actress) of total votes (charts 5 and 6).

For Best Actress in a Leading Role, Julianne Moore secured 36 percent of total votes, making her winner in the survey as well as in reality. However, Marion Cotillard and Rosamund Pike were close runners-up with 26 percent and 22 percent, respectively (chart 7).

Chart 5: Best Performance by an Actor in a Supporting Role

Chart 6: Best Performance by an Actress in a Supporting Role

Chart 7: Best Performance by an Actress in a Leading Role

The biggest surprise was the Best Actor in a Leading Role category. Contrary to the actual win, this survey had Michael Keaton to be in front of Eddie Redmayne. This is noticeable because there is a sharp drop between Keaton with 171 votes (44%) to Redmayne with only 92 votes (24%) (chart 8).

Chart 8: Best Performance by an Actor in a Leading Role

Even if we correlate these results with country of origin or sex, Michael Keaton is still in the lead. However, there is a stronger bias towards Keaton when looking only at the voters from the USA. Bradley Cooper also attracts more attention perhaps due to the more US-specific topic of *American Sniper*. In reverse, both nominees from the United Kingdom received less votes from the US voters compared to the total results, which becomes very clear for Benedict Cumberbatch in *The Imitation Game* (chart 9).

Chart 9: Best Leading Actor correlated to country of origin

When we correlate the votes to the voter's sex, it becomes evident that more female than male voters casted their ballot in favor of Eddie Redmayne and Benedict Cumberbatch instead of Keaton and Cooper (chart 10).

Chart 10: Best Leading Actor correlated to sex

Directing and Writing

There is a significant disagreement in the vital categories of Directing, Adapted Screenplay, and Original Screenplay. For Directing, the survey saw *Boyhood* in the lead and *Birdman* only in second place with a difference of 40 votes (chart 11). Likewise, *Birdman* was only second in the Best Original Screenplay category, with *The Grand Budapest Hotel* in advance (chart 13).

For Best Adapted Screenplay, the choice for *The Imitation Game* was not foreseen at all by the survey. Here, only 52 participants voted for, and the majority saw *Whiplash* in the lead (chart 12).

Chart 11: Best Achievement in Directing

Chart 12: Best Writing, Adapted Screenplay

Chart 13: Best Writing, Original Screenplay

Below-the-line Categories

For most of the so-called technical or below-the-line categories, the survey results were the same like the actual results. The most equal distribution of votes occurred in the Cinematography category. Although *Birdman* won the competition, votes for *The Grand Budapest Hotel* and *Mr. Turner* were unusually strong—thus reflecting the outstanding achievements that were done in these films (chart 14). The same applies for Best Film Editing. Here you can see that it was basically a decision between complex in-scene editing (*Whiplash*) and whole sequence editing (*Boyhood*) with *The Grand Budapest Hotel* in the third place (chart 15).

Chart 14: Best Achievement in Cinematography

Chart 15: Best Achievement in Film Editing

For both the Sound Mixing and the Visual Effects category, it seems that the winners benefitted from the instances that there was no clear runner-up in the field of nominees. Especially for Best Sound Mixing, three films (*American Sniper*, *Birdman*, and *Interstellar*) got 47 to 73 votes and thus rendered

themselves harmless while *Unbroken* was left far behind. On the other hand, *Whiplash* is a film that draws heavy on music. That makes it a strong contender in this field, anyway (charts 16 and 17).

Chart 16: Best Achievement in Sound Mixing

Chart 17: Best Achievement in Visual Effects

There were four categories in the survey which faced strong majorities. *The Grand Budapest Hotel* was the winner in all four categories with approval ratings well over 50 percent (except for Best Original Score). Alas, in the Scoring category it is remarkable that Alexandre Desplat managed to win despite the fact that he was nominated twice (also for *The Imitation Game*) and therefore competing against himself (charts 18 – 21).

Chart 18: Best Achievement in Costume Design

Chart 19: Best Achievement in Makeup and Hairstyling

Chart 20: Best Achievement in Music, Original Score

Chart 21: Best Achievement in Production Design

There were two categories, however, in which the voters of the survey failed to predict the actual winners. For Best Original Song, the final result was pretty close with *The Lego Movie* advancing with only seven votes (chart 22). (During the voting process, this was a category which seemed likely to produce a tie in the end.) For Best Sound Editing, *American Sniper*, which won the actual award, came only third in the survey's voting but again very close to the second place (chart 23).

Chart 22: Best Achievement in Music, Original Song

Chart 23: Best Achievement in Sound Editing

Animated and Documentary Feature, Shorts, and Foreign Language

All these categories have in common that a relatively huge number of voters did not cast any votes. Especially in the three short film categories (Animated, Documentary, and Live Action), about 45 percent of all voters abstained. A possible explanation is that these films are not well-known to the general public. This problem is not restricted to the survey. We can assume that also the majority of Academy members do not know much about these films and thus we may find a high number of non-voters in the Academy roster, too.

For Best Animated Feature, the voters of this survey preferred *The Tale of the Princess Kaguya*. The actual winner *Big Hero 6* finished only third (chart 24).

Chart 24: Best Animated Feature Film

However, if we compare the voting performances of the US voters only, we see though *The Tale of the Princess Kaguya* stays ahead, the actual award winner *Big Hero 6* finishes second at least (chart 25).

Chart 25: Best Animated Feature Film correlated to country of origin

Regarding the Documentary categories, CitizenFour was considered the favorite option for the Academy Awards which is reflected accurately in the survey (chart 26).

Chart 26: Best Documentary Feature

For Best Documentary Short it was a very close neck-to-neck race between *Crisis Hotline: Veterans Press 1* and *White Earth* with only one vote advance. However, when we have again a closer look on the voter's country of origin, *Crisis Hotline* is well in advance ahead of *White Earth*. The possible reason for this is that *Crisis Hotline* deals with a very specific US-American topic. Therefore, the majority of the Academy members voted for *Crisis Hotline* instead of the other nominees (charts 27 and 28).

Chart 27: Best Documentary, Short Subject

Chart 28: Best Documentary, Short Subject correlated to country of origin

For Foreign Language Film, *Ida* was considered the favorite choice of the Academy which was also predicted correctly by the survey voters (chart 29).

Chart 29: Best Foreign Language Film

For both of the Short Film categories, there was a strong favorite in the survey for one film, respectively, while other films received equally distributed votes. Both winners were predicted right (charts 30 and 31).

Chart 30: Best Short Film, Animated

Chart 31: Best Short Film, Live Action

Abstention from Voting

In the survey, each voter was encouraged to vote in all of the 24 categories but was not forced to do so. Instead, if someone did not feel qualified enough to judge he was advised to abstain from voting. This is compliant to the Academy procedures. Some Academy rules even restrict final voting only to those members who have viewed all of the nominated films. This applies to all Documentary and Short Film categories as well as to the Foreign Language Film category (AMPAS 2014, 12, 14, 17, and 27). Therefore it is hardly a surprise when we compare the portion of non-voters throughout all categories.

Chart 32: Abstention from voting in percent per category

For this explorative study, we counted every ballot regardless if it was marked “finished” or not in the survey system. A ballot counts as “finished” when all pages of the survey have been visited and the final page of the survey has been reached. Some voters did vote on the first pages but dropped out somewhere in the middle of the survey without finishing it. Because it was not mandatory to fill out every category, we decided to count every vote that was made and treated unfinished ballots as equally valid as finished ones.

However, to compare abstention from voting we need to distinguish between voters who deliberately abstained and those who simply quit the survey right in the middle. Therefore, in chart 32 we have plotted two values for each category describing the share of non-voters in all ballots and in those that were marked as finished, respectively.

There are only a few non-voters in the major categories. The portion of non-voters is relatively high in the Sound categories as well as in Animated Feature, Original Song, Foreign Language Film, and Documentary Feature (approx. 9 to 20 percent). The three Short Film categories do suffer most from non-voters (around 38 percent).

These results are no surprise at all. Sound is a very different craft to judge. Considering that many Academy members will watch movie screeners (that is, DVDs or online streams provided by the Academy for consideration purposes and sent along with the ballots), not all members will use a high-end sound facility when watching the films. Movies are still considered as a mainly visual medium and movie sound is largely underestimated. Likewise, many Academy members are not familiar with foreign films (which also have not necessarily to be shown in the USA to be eligible in this special category) or in rather marginal genres like documentary or short film. Therefore many will not cast a vote here. Apparently, more or less the same applies for the voters on this survey.

Conclusions

This study was only explorative and therefore cannot be regarded as representative. The sample differs from the Academy roster especially in age matters and sample size. However, despite of these limitations the results were more significant than expected. 15 out of 24 categories have been predicted in a right way. For the remaining categories, the actual winners of the Academy Awards finished at least third or even second.

However, for a future study some adjustments should be made. It could be useful to modify balloting in that way that voters had to pre-register. In doing so, a dedicated survey panel could be created

and final voting would take place by a special invitation only. Thus, everyone on the panel can only vote once and the ballot is inaccessible for outsiders making the conditions even more akin to the Academy membership and voting.

In a nutshell, the Academy voting seems to be predictable in a quite reliable way. The conclusion is that, apparently, voting attitudes do not differ much between the Academy members and those who voted on this survey.

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Notice

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References

- AMPAS (2014): Rules. 87th Annual Academy Awards of Merit for Achievements during 2014. <http://www.oscars.org/sites/default/files/87aa_rules.pdf> (Feb 26, 2015)
- Holden, Anthony (1993): Behind the OSCAR. The Secret History of the Academy Awards. New York: Simon & Schuster.
- LA Times (2012): Unmasking the Academy. Oscar voters overwhelmingly white, male. In: Los Angeles Times, February 19. <<http://www.latimes.com/entertainment/envelope/oscars/la-et-unmasking-oscar-academy-project-20120219-story.html>> (Feb 26, 2015)
- Variety (2015): Oscar Ballot: Six Things for Voters to Know. In: Variety, February 6. <<http://variety.com/2015/film/news/oscar-ballot-six-things-for-voters-to-know-1201419870/>> (Feb 26, 2015)